

Supplementary Table 1: Demographic and clinical data from 14 patients, for each of the *P. aeruginosa* isolates used in this study.

	Patients (N=14)
Age (years), mean (SD)	11.1 (3.1)
Female, n (%)	8 (57.1)
DeltaF508 homozygous, n (%)	7 (50)
Pancreatic insufficient, n (%)	14 (100)
ppFEV ₁ , median (range)	94.5 (50-123)
BMI, median (range)	19.3 (14.5-38)

Supplementary Table 2: Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) using broth microdilution for colistin sulphate, levofloxacin and tobramycin of all 14 isolates grown planktonically.

Isolate	Colistin	Levofloxacin	Tobramycin
ATCC 27853	4	1	1
PA50	8	1	4
PA263	4	1	2
PA288	8	1	1
PA325	8	1	124
PA342	4	1	2
PA375	8	1	1
PA380	2	8	1
PA404	8	2	1
PA505	8	4	1
PA549	2	1	1
PA551	4	1	8
PA558	8	1	2
PA565	4	1	2
PA580	4	2	4

Supplementary Figure 1: Mean OD₆₀₀ readings as assessed by the Crystal Violet assay for each of the *P. aeruginosa* isolates used in this study.

Figure 1. Biofilm biomass quantification by crystal violet assay across 14 clinical *P. aeruginosa* strains. Control (black bars), those treated with 0.1 mg/mL of PelA_h (white bars) or 0.1 mg/mL PslG_h (grey bars). Statistical significance for each treatment relative to its paired untreated control was determined using two-tailed paired t-tests. Asterisks indicate significance levels: p < 0.05 (*), p < 0.01 (**), p < 0.001 (***), p < 0.0001 (****).

Supplementary Figure 2: Confocal microscopy results for PA342 (PslG_h-disrupted strain) with individual vs combination GH therapy.

Figure 2. Live cell biovolume of PA342 following treatment with antibiotics ± single or combination GH. Antibiotic concentrations: colistin (8, 40 µg/mL), levofloxacin (100, 500 µg/mL), tobramycin (100, 500 µg/mL). Horizontal stripes represent LB alone, white bars indicate antibiotic alone, light grey bars represent low-dose PslG_h (0.1 mg/mL), dark grey bars represent high-dose PslG_h (0.5 mg/mL). Diagonal stripes represent combination GH treatment (PslG_h + PelA_h) at low (0.1 mg/mL each) or high (0.5 mg/mL each) concentrations. Bars represent means ± SEM of three biological replicates, each comprising four technical replicates. Statistical comparisons were performed by paired t-tests for antibiotic + single GH and antibiotic + combination GH.

Supplementary Figure 3: Confocal microscopy results for PA380 (PelA_h-disrupted strain) with individual vs combination GH therapy.

(b.)

Figure 3. Live cell biovolume of PA380 following treatment with antibiotics ± single or combination GH. Antibiotic concentrations: colistin (8, 40 µg/mL), levofloxacin (100, 500 µg/mL), tobramycin (200, 1000 µg/mL). Horizontal stripes represent LB alone, white bars indicate antibiotic alone, light grey bars represent low-dose PelA_h (0.1 mg/mL), dark grey bars represent high-dose PelA_h (0.5 mg/mL). Diagonal stripes represent combination GH treatment (PsiG_h + PelA_h) at low (0.1 mg/mL each) or high (0.5 mg/mL each) concentrations. Bars represent means ± SEM of three biological replicates, each comprising four technical replicates. Statistical comparisons were performed by paired t-tests to compare antibiotic + single GH vs. antibiotic + combination GH. *p<0.05.

Supplementary Table 3: Percent of biofilm reduction by each GH as assessed by 1 hour disruption assay with crystal violet compared to the corresponding control well with no GH.

Strain + GH	Sputum Supernatant (%)	0 h	4 h	20 h
PAO1 + PslG_h	0%	47.5 ± 5.1	69.3 ± 3.8	30.0 ± 7.3
	10%	42.9 ± 11.9	67.0 ± 3.7	10.6 ± 4.3
	20%	64.3 ± 3.3	65.6 ± 4.4	11.1 ± 8.3
PA14 + PelA_h	0%	11.5 ± 3.5	10.8 ± 2.9	0.4 ± 4.3
	10%	10.4 ± 11.2	1.9 ± 8.4	-21.1 ± 7.7
	20%	11.8 ± 8.9	-5.6 ± 5.6	-27.2 ± 6.2

Supplementary Table 3. Residual biofilm-disrupting activity following pre-incubation of PslG_h or PelA_h in CF sputum supernatant. Values are shown as mean ± SEM from 6 technical replicates and are provided descriptively to illustrate trends in residual activity after sputum exposure.